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Abstract E-Book

RF01-14

Anterior segment ischemia following intra-arterial chemotherapy for stage E retinoblastoma: report of four cases

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Purpose: To report two new cases of anterior segment ischemia following intra-arterial chemotherapy alone and two cases after intra-arterial and intra-vitreous chemotherapy in retinoblastoma stage E1.

Method: Observational case series of four patients with stage E1 retinoblastoma. The clinical records of patients diagnosed with retinoblastoma were retrospectively reviewed. We obtained anterior segment and fundus photography (Panocam). We document the effects of anterior segment ischemia by MRI and histological examination.

Results: We registered anterior segment ischemia in 4 cases out of 304 who underwent intra-arterial chemotherapy; two of them have been treated also with intra-vitreous chemotherapy. All of them developed iris atrophy or subatrophy, cataract and neovascular glaucoma.

Conclusion: Only four cases of anterior segment ischemia after intra-arterial chemotherapy are reported in literature. We present two new cases of anterior segment ischemia following intra-arterial chemotherapy alone and two cases after intra-arterial and intra-vitreous chemotherapy. This is a possible complication that should be considered by the clinician in patients that undergo first- or second-line IAC.

cedure usually gives excellent results in preventing recurrence, maintaining the structural integrity of the anterior segment, and maintaining good visual function.

RF01-15

Surgical treatment of iris lesions

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Purpose: The most frequent iris lesions seen in routine clinical practice are nevocellular nevi, iris melanocytomas, “suspicious” nevocellular nevi–melanocytic neoplasia of uncertain malignant potential, and iris melanoma. Due to their localization, iris lesions are easily observed by clinical ophthalmological examination. They grow slowly and usually require only documented and regular monitoring. However, if necessary, surgical excision is one of the preferred therapeutic modalities with good results.

Method: Forty-nine patients were surgically treated and monitored for iris lesions at the University Eye Hospital Clinical Center of Serbia. In patients who underwent surgery, the entire lesion was removed, and the iris and/or pupil was reshaped (iridoplasty and/or pupilloplasty). Simultaneous or (rarely) subsequent cataract surgery using phacoemulsification in combination with artificial intraocular lens implantation has also been performed.

Results: The most common histopathological findings included melanoma and melanocytic neoplasia with uncertain malignant potential, several nevocellular nevi, melanocytomas, and one iris varix. Excellent tumor control was maintained throughout patient follow-up while maintaining good visual acuity and vision quality in each case.

Conclusion: Iris lesions are easily accessible for clinical ophthalmological examination and are relatively easy to recognize and monitor. In some cases, surgical removal of these lesions is the preferred treatment option. This pro-

EP-CAT-42

Trifocal IOLs implantation in cataract patients that have experienced previous laser vision correction*M. Piovella¹, B. Kusa¹**¹Piovella Global Center For Ophthalmology, Ophthalmology, Monza, Italy*

Purpose: To evaluate visual performances of trifocal IOLs AT LISA tri 839 MP and AT LISA tri toric 939MP trifocal IOLs (Carl Zeiss Meditec AG - Jena - Germany) in patient that experienced previous laser vision correction.

Methods: Only eyes with regular cornea were included in this study:

36 eyes of 21 patients mean age:

56.57 ± 8.76 years. Preop SE was -0.91 ± 3,31 BCDVA 20/21.40 ± 3,18.

Postop were measured: distance (5m) near (40cm) and intermediate (80 cm) VA, corneal topography and aberrometry, contrast sensitivity and defocus curve and quality of vision. Follow-up examinations were performed at day 1 2 7 30 90 180 360 and yearly.

Results: At six months BCDVA was 20/20,65 ± 2,51. SE was -0,20 ± 0,45. Residual astigmatism was 0,02 ± 0,42.83% of eyes after trifocal IOLs implantation achieved postop refractive results within ± 0.75 diopters.

Conclusion: Trifocal IOLs provided good visual performances also with patients that experienced laser vision correction decades ago. To be selected for surgery eyes biometry needed to be applied with no difficulties and hav to demonstrate no significant differences related the perfect IOLs power also after multiple attempts.

EP-CAT-43

Paulus Aeginetus, a Byzantine physician of the 7th century and his contribution to ophthalmology*G. Balanikas¹, D. Peirounides¹, S. Diafas¹, I. Voudouragaki¹, E. Papadopoulou¹, N. Makris², D. Christodoulou³, ¹Society of History of Ophthalmology Scholars¹**¹Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, A¹ Ophthalmologic Clinic, AHEPA Hospital, Thessaloniki, Greece, ²Ophthalmiatreio Athinon, A¹ Ophthalmologic Clinic, Athens, Greece, ³Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Department of Medicine, Laboratory of History of Medicine, Thessaloniki, Greece*

Purpose: This presentation is to exhibit the work of the Byzantine physician Paulus Aeginetus and especially his contribution to treating ophthalmic conditions such as cataract, glaucoma, trauma, and other diseases. It is believed that he was born on the Greek island of Aegina c. 625 A.D.

Methods: A classic medical text of the middle Byzantine period was a valuable source for medieval medical knowledge, but very little was known about its author. The work is 'The Seven Books of Paulus Aegineta' or 'Epitome Medicae' This work is a compendium of ancient and byzantine medical knowledge, and it was the basis for the development of the knowledge of late Arabic Medicine.

This presentation was based mainly on the Sixth book of this 3-volume compendium of English Edition in 1834, published by Francis Adams, which includes the Ophthalmologic issues.

Results: 'πτομαί ιατρικαί' is the original title of Paulus Aegineta's work. Three manuscripts from Paulus's work are kept in the Megisti Lavra monastery of Mount Athos library. This library was established around 963 A.D.

by St. Athanasius, founder of the conventus life of Mt. Athos. Fragments of Paulus's work are also in the monastery of Iviron on Mt. Athos. Paulus Aeginetus was the only physician of the ancients who described the cataract operation. He also described burns of the eyelids by drugs and the subsequent creation of a symblepharon (Συμβλήφαρον).

Conclusion: Paulus Aegineta's life is entirely unknown, but his monumental work gives us a rich encounter with Medicine not only during the 7th century but also before and after him and is one of the main sources of medical knowledge for the upcoming generations of physicians.

The 6th book of this work includes several ophthalmological conditions such as eyelid disorders, chalazion, pterygium, trichiasis, cataract, glaucoma, and the diagnosis, medications, and treatment for them. Paulus Aeginetus (625-690 A.D.) was considered one of the great compilers of Medical Knowledge.

EP-CAT-44

Central macular thickness changes following laser posterior capsulotomy measured by optical coherence tomography*D. Vasovic¹, D. Rasic¹, I. Marjanovic¹**¹University Eye Hospital Clinical Centre of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia*

Purpose: Neodymium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet (Nd: YAG) laser treatment is considered the gold standard for posterior capsule opacification (PCO) treatment. However, it can lead to complications such as increased intraocular pressure (IOP), retinal hemorrhage, iritis, vitreous prolapse, corneal injury, vitritis, pupil blockage, hyphema, retinal detachment, IOL dislocation, exacerbation of endophthalmitis, and cystoid macular edema.

Our study aimed to access changes in the central macular thickness (CMT) at different time points following Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy using optical coherence tomography (OCT).

Method: This study included 112 eyes (59 males and 53 females) from pseudophakic patients with PCO. Patients with other anterior or posterior segment pathologies were excluded from this study. The CMT values were measured at baseline, one week, one month, 3 and 6 months following Nd: YAG capsulotomy. The preoperative and postoperative measurements were compared. SPSS 21.0 was used for statistical analysis, and a difference was considered significant if $p < 0.05$. All values are expressed as means ± SD.

Results: The mean age of all patients was 76±9.12 years. After treatment, best-corrected visual acuity was significantly higher than baseline values ($p < 0.05$).

On the other hand, significant changes related to age, gender, total laser shots, total laser energy, and time between cataract surgery and Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy was not observed ($p > 0.05$).

The mean CMT values at baseline, one week, one month, 3 and 6 months following Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy were 256.11 ± 16.001, 267.69 ± 17.012, 266.08 ± 16.015, 260.08 ± 16.015, 257.08 ± 16.015 μm, respectively. Cystoid macular edema developed in 2 patients (1.78%).

Conclusion: Significant changes in CMT values following Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy was not observed compared to the baseline. However, cystoid macular edema remains one of the possible causes of visual reduction following Nd: YAG laser capsulotomy.

EP-GLA-41

Outcomes of Gonioscopy-assisted Transluminal Trabeculotomy (GATT) surgery in patients with glaucoma

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Purpose: To report outcomes of gonioscopy-assisted transluminal trabeculotomy (GATT) surgery in patients with glaucoma.

Methods: A retrospective review was performed for all patients who underwent GATT surgery in a third level hospital. Main outcome measures were IOP, number of glaucoma medications and IOP reduction.

Results: 84 eyes were treated. The mean age was 69.34 years (15.98 standard deviation). 65.5% of surgeries were performed in males. Most procedures were performed during 2022 (39.3%) and 2019 (28.6%). GATT surgery was performed, most frequent like a combined surgery (67,9% Phacoemulsification + GATT), mainly in patients with open angle glaucoma (70.2%) and angle-closure glaucoma (17.9%).

For all eyes, the mean preoperative intraocular pressure (IOP) (SD) was 22.95 (8.47) mm Hg, and 2.69 (0.07) glaucoma medications. Mean postoperative IOP was 13.81 (3.44) at 6 months. There were just 5 complicated cases (2 hyphema, 1 descemet detachment, 1 hemovitreal, and 1 uveitis). Visual acuity changed from 0.4 to 1 post surgery.

When the groups were divided based on combined (PHACO + GATT) or GATT surgery, there were no statistically significant difference in age, pre surgical number of glaucoma medications, pre- and post-surgical visual acuity, mean IOP.

Conclusions: GATT is a safe and successful surgery for different types of glaucoma, especially in open angle glaucoma. GATT offer an important IOP decrease in patients at 6 months follow-up.

EP-GLA-42

Changes in peripapillary retinal nerve fiber layer thickness in chronic glaucoma and non-glaucoma patients after phacoemulsification cataract surgery

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Purpose: The effect of cataract surgery on the retinal nerve fiber layer (RNFL) and central macular thickness (CMT), causing their alteration, has been shown in a few previously published reports.

Our study aimed to determine changes in the RNFL and CMT in primary chronic glaucoma patients and healthy subjects following uncomplicated phacoemulsification surgery.

Method: This study included 65 eyes from primary chronic glaucoma patients whose intraocular pressure (IOP) had been treated for a long term with or without medications (IOP \leq 20mmHg) and 59 eyes from healthy controls. The average RNFL thickness and CMT were assessed using spectral-domain

optical coherence tomography (SD-OCT). Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS21.0, and the difference was considered significant if $p < 0.05$. All values are expressed as means \pm SD.

Results: The mean age of all patients was 69 \pm 10.62 years. The average RNFL thickness in glaucoma patients preoperatively, at one week, one month, and six months postoperatively were 96.8 \pm 19.0, 99.9 \pm 20.1, 98.3 \pm 19.2 and 96.4 \pm 21.1 μ m, respectively.

On the other hand, the average RNFL thickness in control group patients were 100.9 \pm 10.4, 102.3 \pm 7.7, 103.0 \pm 5.6, and 100.3 \pm 4.1 μ m, respectively. The mean CMT values in glaucoma patients preoperatively, at one week, one month, and six months postoperatively were 255.11 \pm 16.001, 266.69 \pm 17.012, 264.09 \pm 18.055, 255.08 \pm 16.015 μ m, respectively. The corresponding values of the control group were 255.16 \pm 16.111, 265.59 \pm 16.003, 265.12 \pm 17.066, 255.08 \pm 15.021 μ m, respectively.

Significant differences in the average RNFL thickness and CMT values between these two groups preoperatively and at all three-time points postoperatively were not observed ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: Phacoemulsification increased peripapillary RNFL thickness and CMT in both groups at one week and one month postoperatively. However, these values were not significantly different between these groups.

EP-GLA-43

Clear as mud - a diagnostic and therapeutic challenge

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We describe a case of a 44-year-old Caucasian man with an ophthalmological history of LASIK (only OD) 15 years ago for a high myopia (OD-9.00D and OS-8.00D) and mild astigmatism (OD-1.75D and OS-2.25D), currently wearing contact lenses. He has history of controlled hypertension, Ischemic Stroke, Obstructive Sleep Apnea and reports eye steroid use for 6 months 20 years ago for a condition he couldn't remember. He was referred to the Glaucoma department because of bilateral total disc cupping with a corresponding floor effect on SD-OCT.

On our examination he presented a MAVC OU of 0.1 LogMAR and a wide anterior chamber with no pathological findings. Intraocular Pressure (IOP) on Goldmann's tonometer was 15/16 mmHg, and gonioscopy showed an open angle (Grade IV Shaffer) with no posterior convexity of the iris. Fundoscopy of both eyes showed an optic disc with total but apparently shallow cupping, with no such pallor; and temporal peripapillary atrophy.

US Pachymetry was 544 μ mOD and 542 μ mOS. Macular SD-OCT was normal as well as the macular Ganglion Cell Complex (GCC) of the right eye, but left eye showed a diffuse loss of the GCC. Automated standard static perimetry (30°) revealed an inferior nasal step OD and OS and an upper arcuate scotoma OS, with deficits not sparing vertical axis. His ophthalmological history (refractive laser surgery influencing pachymetry and measured value of IOP; high myopia with alterations of the disc and retina that may influence interpretation of the OCT, history of topical steroid drops and past stroke) and the degree of agreement between the exams (OCT and Perimetry) make this case a complex diagnostic and therapeutic challenge.

Assuming a possible normal-pressure glaucoma, ABPM and CT of head and orbits scans were requested (without alterations), and an IOP measurement curve was performed for 12 hours with no peaks or oscillations (mean IOP16/17 mmHg). The patient is currently being followed up, without therapy and with no disease progression.

EP-NEO-33

"Apex Predator": a case of Orbital Apex Syndrome secondary to Invasive Fungal Rhinosinusitis in the setting of a COVID-19 pandemic

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This is a case of a 39-year-old female, diabetic with poor control, diagnosed case of COVID-19 treated symptomatically at home. After recovery, patient experienced left-sided facial numbness and anisocoria. Patient seen and admitted by neurology service at a tertiary medical institution. Orbit-MRI done revealed Cellulitis vs Pseudotumor of Left Orbit and Pansinusitis.

During admission, new onset of gaze palsies with mild proptosis of the left eye noted. Patient initially treated as a case of orbital cellulitis-left eye and treated with Intravenous antibiotics and steroids. No response to treatment noted. Lack of funds led to discharge against medical advice. Months passed and follow up done with new onset of decreased visual acuity (hand movement-left), yellow-green nasal discharge, and anosmia.

Patient admitted and imaging revealed a Polysinonasal disease, left maxillary, sphenoid sinuses with erosive changes. Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery (FESS) and Histopathology of Sinus specimen done revealing a diagnosis of Mucormycosis. Patient was started on Intravenous anti-fungal. Post-management, return of normal ocular motility and improvement of visual acuity achieved.

Only time will tell vision of the patient will return to baseline.

Socioeconomic factors contribute greatly to the outcome of our patients, and as physicians the challenge arises to be as concise and accurate as possible to get only the necessary tools for us to make an accurate and timely assessment. Limited resource settings make it difficult to have the necessary diagnostics done for patients, but keen observation and a good history may be the difference between life and death for patients.

Sticking to basics is always a good idea when managing patients.

EP-NEO-34

Incidental finding of a space-occupying intracranial vascular lesion secondary to visual field defect

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Internal carotid aneurysms can show up with variable symptoms depending on their location, but is infrequent to do it ophthalmologically.

An 80-year-old woman with visual field loss in her left eye (LE) is referred by her primary care physician for ophthalmologic evaluation. As a cardiovascular risk factor, she has arterial hypertension under treatment and has aortic insufficiency under cardiology follow-up. In the ophthalmological examination of both eyes (BE), we found a visual acuity of 0.7 and diffuse pigmentary dispersion, guttas and stable pseudophakia in the slit lamp.

Intraocular pressure was 14 mmHg in BE and in funduscopy and retinography exams we found diffuse papillary pallor, greater in the temporal quadrant of the right eye (RE) and in the nasal quadrant of the LE and excavation of 0.2, being normal the rest of the exam. A visual field was performed where a congruent left homonymous hemianopsia was evidenced, so he was priority

referred to the hospital to complete the examination. The study was completed with a macular optical coherence tomography (mOCT) that was normal in BE, an OCT of the peripapillary fiber layer where was observed a decrease in temporal thickness in RE and in nasal quadrant in LE with a decreased mean thickness in BE.

Priority cranial computed tomography (CT) and CT angiography were performed, where a partially thrombosed giant right carotid aneurysm was detected with a mass effect on the adjacent brain structures. Also, was done a cerebral arteriography where aneurysms were observed in both carotids and in the right posterior cerebral artery and a Doppler ultrasound of the supra-aortic trunks that was normal. Due to the risk-benefit balance, the management was conservative.

The ophthalmologist plays an important role in the diagnosis of these lesions as they can cause a ophthalmological alteration as first symptom, furthermore it can manifest as an atypical campimetric alteration depending on the magnitude of the lesion.

EP-NEO-35

Perioperative ischemic optic neuropathy

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Ischemic optic neuropathy (ION) can be a consequence of some long-term surgical procedures. It is usually bilateral and can be anterior (AION) or posterior (PION). A number of possible risk factors are cited.

We present a case of male patient, injured in a traffic accident at the age of 35. After a four-hour operation for head injuries and a long recovery in a difficult general condition, the patient noticed bilateral vision problems. There is more prominent visual loss on his right eye with upper altitudinal visual field defect, and a lower altitudinal defect on the left, better eye. Findings correspond to the condition after AION.

The consequences are shown through the results of functional and morphological damage to the optic nerves. The paper also analyzes the possible contribution of other risk factors to the occurrence of this condition.

EP-ONC-10

Intense ocular pain as the first symptom of metastatic lung cancer

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Choroidal metastases are the first cause of malignant intraocular tumor and are usually multifocal. When symptomatic they present with decreased visual acuity and visual alterations. We present the case of a 76-year-old man with a painful choroidal mass as the first manifestation of a lung cancer.

He complained of a 1-month history of intense ocular pain and had a violaceous and painful sectoral hyperemia with no other signs of inflammation. The fundus examination showed a single large yellowish choroidal mass in the posterior-superior-nasal quadrant. No Kappa angle or subretinal fluid was seen on ultrasonography and there was no double circulation pattern on fluorescein angiography. Magnetic resonance imaging revealed a T1 and T2 hypointense choroidal mass, with heterogeneous contrast enhancement. In view of the presentation, giant nodular scleritis was considered and empirical treatment with corticosteroids was initiated.

Nevertheless, further studies were also performed to rule out an amelanotic melanoma or choroidal metastasis. In the end, radiological imaging tests revealed a lung mass that confirmed the diagnosis of choroidal lung metastasis.

A single painful choroidal mass can be the first manifestation of a lung cancer, urging the ophthalmologist to stay alert and perform the pertinent studies.

EP-ONC-11

Ocular toxicity following carboplatin chemotherapy for neuroendocrine tumour of the bladder – a case report

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Introduction: Carboplatin is a commonly used platinum analogue chemotherapeutic agent that is similar to cisplatin, however is known to be better tolerated. This case report outlines a case of Ocular Toxicity following Carboplatin chemotherapy used for the management of a neuroendocrine tumour of the bladder.

Case report: A 70-year-old man presented four weeks following his fourth chemotherapy cycle with a one-week history of right eye blurriness. The man was undergoing chemotherapy with Etoposide and Carboplatin for a neuroendocrine tumour of the bladder. Two weeks following his third chemotherapy cycle, the patient suffered a similar episode of visual changes in his left eye, raising suspicion for Carboplatin-Induced Ocular Toxicity. After cessation of the Carboplatin chemotherapy, the patient's vision remained stable.

Discussion: Although the current literature on Carboplatin-Induced Ocular Toxicity remains scanty, previous cases have reported symptoms beginning

five days to two weeks following Carboplatin use. Metamorphopsia, altered colour vision and blind spots have been reported as forms of visual disturbance in previous literature. This case report discussed an example of bilateral sequential loss of vision following Carboplatin chemotherapy for a neuroendocrine tumour of the bladder.

Conclusion: It remains critical for ophthalmologists and oncologists to look out for ocular side effects of chemotherapy due to its devastating effects.

EP-ONC-12

Less is more: new one-step intracameral chemotherapy technique

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Purpose: To describe the feasibility of a new one-step approach to aspirate the aqueous and apply melphalan in a single-go without repeated entries into the anterior chamber.

Methods: This retrospective non-comparative study was conducted at a referral center and included 12 patients. The one-step approach is described in a step-wise manner. No complications were observed among the patients.

Results: One single injection of intracameral melphalan proved to be a successful treatment in nine cases. Two patients required a second injection, which was administered two weeks after the first one following the same technique.

Conclusions: This proved to be a reasonable technique for the smooth application of melphalan in the anterior chamber studded with retinoblastoma seeds. Our outcomes revealed that it is an effective, quick, and cost-effective technique. Longer-term data collection is underway, though initial findings are encouraging.

EP-ONC-13

Report of a case and review of iris vascular anomalies

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Purpose: Vascular lesions or anomalies of the iris stroma are generally considered to be quite rare and benign. They can be congenital or acquired, primary or secondary, isolated or with systemic associations, true neoplasms or simulating lesions, or hamartomas. Treatment choices for those vascular lesions are not standardized and should be tailored for each patient individually.

Case presentation: Vascular lesions of the iris stroma are generally considered to be quite rare and benign. A 77-year-old woman was referred to the hospital with a 6-month history of blurred vision and a mild discomfort in her right eye caused by spontaneous recurrent hyphema and a transient rise of intraocular pressure (IOP) due to a pigmented iris mass, as it was reported by a local ophthalmologist.

Anterior segment examination of the right eye revealed corneal epithelial edema, 2 mm of hyphema, and scattered/dispersed red blood cells in the anterior chamber. Right eye ultrasound biomicroscopy revealed an iris lesion at the

EP-ONC-19

Comparison of two primary intraocular lymphoma experimental murine models

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Purpose: The research on experimental models of primary intraocular lymphoma (PIOL) helps to elucidate the pathophysiology of the disease and to find new therapeutical strategies. The purpose of this project was to compare the characteristics of two experimental murine models of PIOL.

Methods: PIOL was induced in immunocompetent mice by intravitreal injection of syngeneic DLBCL cell suspension. For mice strain C3H/HeN cell line 38C13 was used, for BALB/CaNn it was cell line A20. Following the injection, mice were monitored clinically 2 times per week. The experiment was terminated at the first signs of exophthalmos or on day 30. Eyes were collected post-mortem and histologically processed.

Results: Both mice strains show a high percentage of PIOL development. Disease progression is faster in C3H/HeN with exophthalmos occurring in all mice no later than day 21, on average on day 11. Vitreous involvement is a predominant sign in the clinical presentation of this group. In BALB/CaNn mice exophthalmos occurs on average on day 22.

At the same time, tumorous infiltration of the retina, tumorous infiltration of the optic disc, and tumorous retinal detachment are dominant signs. The difference in the development of exophthalmos is most probably due to the different affinity of cancer cells for orbital tissue.

Conclusion: PIOL has slower progression in BALB/CaNn strain with later or no occurrence of exophthalmos. The varying time of exophthalmos development is most probably due to the difference between the affinity of 38C13 and A20 cells for orbital tissue.

The primary affinity of the 38C13 cell line for orbital tissue can explain earlier development of exophthalmos in C3H/HeN mice. This and the fact that the PIOL progression is slower in BALB/CaNn strain predisposes the latter to be more suitable for therapeutic experiments planned in the future.

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EP-ONC-20

Uveal melanoma cells exhibit variable growth patterns and distinct mitochondrial respiration profile compared with primary human uveal melanocytes

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Purpose: Uveal melanoma is a deadly cancer with high metastatic potential. Mitochondrial metabolism and epigenetics are known to play a role in tumorigenesis, progression, and metastasis. However, primary human uveal melanocytes are difficult to obtain, and the metabolic state of malignant versus benign uveal melanocytes has not been well characterized.

We describe the morphologic patterns, growth rate, and mitochondrial function of uveal melanoma cell lines compared with successfully isolated primary human uveal melanocytes.

Methods: Primary human uveal melanocytes were isolated from six donor eyes and successfully propagated in 2D cell culture. Photographs were obtained using inverted microscopy. Growth curves were determined using timed seeding and counting. Oxygen consumption under four respiratory states was measured using Seahorse. These were compared with two uveal melanoma cell lines, MP46 (highly adherent), and MP65 (partially suspended). Student t-test and its derivatives were used for statistical analysis as appropriate.

Results: In 2D cell culture, uveal melanoma MP46 and MP65 cell lines formed primitive colonies with light to moderate pigmentation, while primary uveal melanocytes formed higher order patterns with heavy pigmentation.

In addition, uveal melanoma MP46 cells grew faster than PK3 and PK4 benign melanocytes. Metabolically, uveal melanoma MP46 cells showed a glycolytic metabolic profile with statistically significant decrease in basal respiration, increase in proton leak respiration, and decrease in coupling efficiency when compared with PK4 primary uveal melanocytes.

Conclusions: Uveal melanoma cell lines showed distinct morphological, physiologic, and metabolic characteristics compared with benign uveal melanocytes. Interestingly, despite increased growth rate, MP46 uveal melanoma cells showed decreased coupling efficiency compared with PK4 primary uveal melanocytes.

EP-ONC-21

Von Hippel-Lindau disease: a case report and review of literature

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Purpose: Von Hippel-Lindau (VHL) syndrome is a hereditary autosomal dominant disease which affects several organ systems. It is characterized by the development of multiple malignant and/or benign tumors in the central nervous system and internal organs, such as retina, liver, pancreas, reproductive tract, kidneys and adrenal glands.

Case report: Here we present a case report of a young male patient who was diagnosed with VHL syndrome based on the presence of several characteristic lesions affecting brain, kidneys and retina also positive family history for VHL-associated tumors. The patient was diagnosed with an optic nerve head

Spontaneous resolution of a macular hole was obtained with a bridging of the retinal tissue across the hole. After a 2-month check-up, there was an improvement in best corrected visual acuity from 0,5 Snellen to 0,8 Snellen, and the patient no longer complains about metamorphopsia. Further follow-ups are planned with regular optical coherence tomography monitoring.

EP-RET-88

Central retinal thickness changes following uncomplicated phacoemulsification cataract surgery in diabetic patients without retinopathy and nondiabetic patients

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Purpose: The development or worsening of macular edema following cataract surgery in diabetic patients can be attributed to increased inflammatory mediators in the aqueous and vitreous after phacoemulsification. Our study aimed to assess changes in the central macular thickness (CMT) in diabetic patients without retinopathy and nondiabetic patients following uncomplicated phacoemulsification surgery using spectral-domain optical coherence tomography (SD-OCT).

Method: This study included 110 eyes from well-controlled diabetic patients without retinopathy and 99 from healthy controls. CMT values were measured using SD-OCT preoperatively and at one week, one month, three, and six months postoperatively. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS21.0, and the difference was considered significant if $p < 0.05$. All values are expressed as means \pm SD.

Results: The mean age of all patients was 75.52 years. The mean CMT values in well-controlled diabetic patients without retinopathy preoperatively, at one week, one month, and 3 and 6 months postoperatively were 255.02, 19.002, 265.71, 16.090, 264.13, 17.072, 256.12, 16.069, and 255.10, 15.055, respectively. The corresponding values in control group patients were 255.00, 17.811, 264.69, 15.089, 263.11, 16.069, 255.31, 15.076, and 255.09, 16.055, respectively. Significant differences in the mean CMT values between these two groups preoperatively and at all four-time points postoperatively were not observed ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: CMT values increased following uncomplicated cataract surgery at one week and one month postoperatively. However, a significant difference between these groups was not observed.

EP-RET-90

Retinal hemorrhages in the context of thrombocytopenia secondary to azathioprine therapy

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Introduction: It should be noted that prolonged accumulation of blood between the layers of the retina releases biochemical compounds that can cause toxicity and damage to the photoreceptors resulting in permanent visual impairment.

Method: Case report and review of the literature.

Results: We present the case of a 34-year-old man with a diagnosis of Ulcerative Colitis treated with 5-asa, topical Budesonide and Azathioprine (Inmurel).

He was admitted to the Digestive Department on 3/9/22. Laboratory tests showed severe thrombocytopenia. It was suggested that the causative drug was Inmurel.

A few hours after admission, the patient reported blurred vision and myodesopsia in both visual fields. Fundoscopy revealed bilateral peripapillary haemorrhages.

On day 9, he reported a reddish stain, especially with his right eye. He was re-evaluated and pre-retinal bleeding was observed in this eye affecting the pre-macular region, with a similar appearance in the contralateral eye.

When the clinical situation improved, optical coherence tomography and retinography was performed. With visual acuity of 0.05 in the left eye and central scotoma in the right eye, it was decided to perform a hyalodectomy in the most affected eye, the right one, as the contralateral eye had a foveal haemorrhage that prevented laser drainage.

On the 20th day, visual acuity was 0.9 in the right eye. The same bleeding persisted in the left eye. After seven days, only subhyaloid blood remained in the right eye. The blood in the left eye decreased in size and was more dehaemoglobinised, so expectant management is maintained.

At one and a half months the acuity is 0.5 in the left eye, and the tomography shows the haematic remains in the fovea. The course is favourable and the patient can be discharged.

Conclusion: Retinal haemorrhages may occur in the context of severe thrombocytopenia, an early approach to laser hyalodectomy can avoid late vitrectomy and increased complications later on.

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The role of glucose variability in the development of retinal microvascular changes in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus

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Introduction and aim: The aim of the presentation is to emphasize the importance of glucose variability (GV) in the development of retinal microvascular changes in patients with Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM). Using a subcutaneous glucose sensor, the concentration of glucose in subcutaneous tissue is monitored continuously, and the obtained data provide information on the GV over the sensor lifespan (7-14 days).

Methods: The correlation of glucose variability (usually calculated as standard deviation [SD] or coefficient of variation [CV]) with the development of diabetic retinopathy (DR) or its progression to more severe forms is documented on the cases of two patients with T1DM.

Results: A patient with lower GV (SD=2.4 with 82-84% time spent in the target glucose range between 3.9 and 10.0 mmol/l) has no signs of DR. A patient with high GV (SD=5.8 with 52% in the target glucose range between 3.9 and 10.0 mmol/l) developed severe proliferative DR with complications.

Conclusion: Patients not only with poor glucose control, but also with higher GV, have higher risk of developing DR. Continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) using a subcutaneous sensor contributes to better diabetes control